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To Be Neighbours in Our World: Pope Francis' Vision for Humanity and Society in *Fratelli Tutti*

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Abstract: Fratelli Tutti can be considered Pope Francis' manifesto of the "social covenant" of human fraternity and social friendship for modern times. Here, he envisions a society that is open to all, includes all and values all. He invites us to dream together for a society that integrates everyone and fosters interrelatedness and interdependence.

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He visualizes a society that opens to the needs of the world and promotes healthy neighbourhood in the world. He envisages a society that overcomes the evils of intolerance, social exclusion, racism, the culture of “throwaway” and social media. He calls for a society that nurtures a culture of fraternity, dialogue, encounter, and tolerance. He foresees a society that raises human dignity, and fosters opportunity and dignity of human labour. He visualizes a society that develops global ethics of solidarity and cooperation to find solutions for common issues. Fratelli Tutti is Pope Francis’ invitation to “dream together” (FT 127) for “a single human family” (FT 8); his spiritual testament and social manifesto for a better fraternal and universal brotherhood.

Keywords: Fratelli Tutti, Human Fraternity, Interrelatedness, Interdependence, Inclusive.

Introduction

In *Fratelli Tutti*, Pope Francis envisions a global society in which individuals and nations care for one another and acknowledge each human person's dignity. It focuses on contemporary social and economic problems and proposes an ideal world of fraternity in which everyone can be part of a “larger human family” (FT 141).¹ Therefore, he treats this encyclical as a reflection on human fraternity and social friendship as the remedy for the social problems of this world. He makes this clear from the very purpose of this encyclical: “It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity: Brotherhood between all men and women” (FT 8). He encourages

¹ All citations in the text are from Pope Francis, *Fratelli Tutti, Encyclical Letter on Fraternity and Social Friendship*, published by Conference of Catholic Bishops of India (ATC Publishers, Bangalore 2020). Henceforth *Fratelli Tutti* will be abbreviated as FT.

a universal fraternity. However, he says that it demands “a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end” (FT 180). He calls for a “heart open to the whole world” (FT 128-153), a “better kind of politics” (FT 154-197), and “paths of renewed encounter and dialogue” (FT 198-270) for universal fraternity and social friendship. This encyclical is not only an invitation extended to Christians to “dream together” (FT 127) for “a single human family” (FT 8) firmly grounded on human fraternity and social friendship but also to everyone who dreams for it. For he says, “Although I have written it from the Christian convictions that inspire and sustain me, I have sought to make this reflection an invitation to dialogue among all people of good will” (FT 6). Following is an attempt to understand Pope Francis’ vision for humanity and society in *Fratelli Tutti*.

1. An Open, Inclusive, Larger Human Family

Pope Francis’ call for a universal fraternity and dream for a universal human family can be vividly seen at the outset of the encyclical itself:

It is my desire that, in this our time, by acknowledging the dignity of each human person, we can contribute to the rebirth of a universal aspiration to fraternity. Fraternity between all men and women.[...] Let us dream, then, as a single human family, as fellow travellers sharing the same flesh, as children of the same earth which is our common home, each of us bringing the richness of his or her beliefs and convictions, each of us with his or her own voice, brothers and sisters all (FT 8).

Pope Francis notes that “an individual and a people are only fruitful and productive if they are able to develop a creative

openness to others” (FT 41) because we are meant for each other. He believes that “A truly human and fraternal society will be capable of ensuring in an efficient and stable way that each of its members is accompanied at every stage of life. Not only by providing for their basic needs but by enabling them to give the best of themselves...” (FT 110). According to him, “Solidarity means thinking and acting in terms of community. It means that the lives of all are prior to the appropriation of goods by a few. It also means combatting structural causes of poverty, inequality, lack of work, land and housing, the denial of social and labour rights” (FT 116).

Inspired by the words of St. Francis of Assisi, Pope Francis envisages “a love that transcends the barriers of geography and distance” (FT1) because he firmly believes that “a love capable of transcending borders is the basis of... social friendship,” and it is the “genuine social friendship within a society makes true universal openness possible” (FT 99). It is, therefore, he condemns all those who continue to “support varieties of narrow and violent nationalism, xenophobia and contempt, and even the mistreatment of those who are different” (FT 86). Therefore, Pope Francis asks us to create a culture of encounter to get to know one another because he believes that it is not possible “to experience the true beauty of life without relating to others, without having real faces to love” (FT 87). Therefore, he encourages the individuals and nations to open up more, showing gestures of more human fraternity and solidarity (cf. FT 87-90). He believes that “individualism does not make us more free, more equal, more fraternal” (FT 105) but a “universal love” that promotes the dignity of every human being (FT 106-111). According to him, a fundamental familial unity of all humankind is love because “love... impels us towards universal communion” (FT 95). He also says that “the spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love, which in the end remains ‘the criterion for the definitive decision about a human life’s worth or lack thereof’” (FT 92).

Pope Francis sees the need for a larger human family, especially in times of crisis: “The true worth of the different countries of our world is measured by their ability to think not simply as a country but also as part of the larger human family. This is seen especially in times of crisis. Narrow forms of nationalism are an extreme expression of an inability to grasp the meaning of this gratuitousness” (FT 141). He further warns that “only a social and political culture that readily and “gratuitously” welcomes others will have a future” (FT 141).

Pope Francis says that when we fail to recognize each person as a brother or sister, even those “born in the same country” can become “an existential foreigner” (FT 97) or a “hidden exile” (FT 98). A genuinely “human and fraternal” society will work to ensure that every member can thrive at each moment in life (FT 110). This is what it means to “foster integral human development,” a development that promotes the common good and allows us to “advance together towards an authentic and integral growth” (FT 113).

According to Pope Francis, solidarity and social friendship challenge us to place the common good for the universal good. It is in this context that Pope Francis says in Catholic teaching, “the right to private property” is not absolute; it is secondary to the “principle of the universal destination of created goods” (FT 120). This has implications for policies that affect the global poor (e.g., debt relief [FT 126] and access to work opportunities [FT 123]), women (FT 121), migrants (no. 124), and the natural environment (FT 122). He asserts that the global community must place the ability of every human person to thrive over goals of wealth and conquest, “for a real and lasting peace will only be possible ‘on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family’” (FT 127).

In short, Pope Francis says that “we need to think of each other more and more as a single family dwelling in a common home” (FT 87).

According to him, the COVID-19 pandemics once again revealed humanity’s vulnerability and the need to work together globally to tackle a common issue:

True, a worldwide tragedy like the Covid-19 pandemic momentarily revived the sense that we are a global community, all in the same boat, where one person’s problems are the problems of all. Once more we realized that no one is saved alone; we can only be saved together. As I said in those days, “the storm has exposed our vulnerability and uncovered those false and superfluous certainties around which we constructed our daily schedules, our projects, our habits and priorities (FT 32).

Following the invitation to “advance along the paths of hope” (FT 55), Pope Francis offers reflections on the parable of the Good Samaritan as a starting point for our call to universal fraternity: “The parable shows us how a community can be rebuilt by men and women who identify with the vulnerability of others, who reject the creation of a society of exclusion and act instead as neighbours, lifting up and rehabilitating the fallen for the sake of the common good” (FT 67). Pope Francis invites us to take up “co-responsibility” in creating communities built upon solidarity and social friendship: “Today we have a great opportunity to express our innate sense of fraternity, to be Good Samaritans who bear the pain of other people’s troubles rather than fomenting greater hatred and resentment” (FT 77). He reminds us that change happens on the level of ordinary people, and that “each individual can act as an effective leaven by the way he or she lives each day” (FT 231).

Pope Francis reminds us that “God continues to sow abundant seeds of goodness in our human family” (FT 54). He believes that “to be part of a people is to be part of a shared identity arising from social and cultural bonds. And that is not something automatic, but rather a slow, difficult process ... of advancing towards a common project” (FT 158).

2. Society that integrates everyone

Pope Francis envisions a human and fraternal society where everyone is integrated and taken care of. For he says: “A truly human and fraternal society will be capable of ensuring in an efficient and stable way that each of its members is accompanied at every stage of life. Not only by providing for their basic needs, but by enabling them to give the best of themselves, even though their performance may be less than optimum, their pace slow or their efficiency limited” (FT 110). He also visualizes a human and fraternal society characterized by liberty and equality, for he says: “Fraternity is born not only of a climate of respect for individual liberties, or even of a certain administratively guaranteed equality. Fraternity necessarily calls for something greater, which in turn enhances freedom and equality” (FT 103). He says that equality is not achieved by an abstract proclamation that “all men and women are equal” (FT 103). Instead, it is the result of the conscious and careful cultivation of fraternity” (FT 104). He also dreams a human and fraternal society that fosters human dignity: “Social friendship and universal fraternity necessarily call for an acknowledgement of the worth of every human person, always and everywhere” (FT 106). Therefore, he warns that if the human dignity of the elderly, poor, unborn and disabled are not taken care of, then the dream of a universal fraternity will be a vague ideal (FT 18).

Pope Francis urges us to “include or exclude those lying wounded along the roadside” (FT 69) in our community. While reflecting upon the parable of the Good Samaritan, the framework upon which he built *Fratelli Tutti*, he instructs, “Each day we have to decide whether to be Good Samaritans or indifferent bystanders” (FT 69). He explains it in the following way, “Every brother or sister in need, when abandoned or ignored by the society in which I live, becomes an existential foreigner, even though born in the same country. They may be citizens with full rights, yet they are treated like foreigners in their own country” (FT 97).

Strikingly, Pope Francis calls for the creation of a “social covenant” (FT 218) between all members of society, rich and poor, which obliges everyone to give up some things for the common good (FT 219). According to the Pope, “a realistic and inclusive social covenant must also be a “cultural covenant”, one that respects and acknowledges the different worldviews, cultures and lifestyles that coexist in society” (FT 219). He further explains its nature: “Such a covenant also demands the realization that some things may have to be renounced for the common good” (FT 221). Social covenant demands authentic acknowledgement of our neighbour and the ability to “stand in the place of others” (FT 221). He says that “Words like freedom, democracy or fraternity prove meaningless, for only when our economic and social system no longer produces even a single victim, a single person cast aside, will we be able to celebrate the feast of universal fraternity” (FT 110).

Pope Francis also calls for a society that “cultivates kindness” (FT 222), an attitude to be recuperated because it “free us from the cruelty..., anxiety and ...frantic flurry of activity” (FT 224) that prevail in our contemporary age. Pope Francis says that cultivating “kindness” is necessary in order to move beyond mere civility to true social love for our neighbours (FT 224).

3. Society that Fosters Interrelatedness and Interdependence

One of the significant concerns of Pope Francis is humanity's interconnectedness. Therefore, he says that the suffering or impoverishment in part of the globe will not stay confined there: "we are either all saved together or no one is saved" (FT 137). He speaks of a "universal consciousness" that creates a mutual concern for the well-being of the earth and those most impacted by injustices occurring within it (FT 117). He reminds us of our interrelatedness, saying: "No one people, culture, or individual can achieve everything on its own: to attain fulfilment in life we need others" (FT 150). A feeling of interconnectedness must remain central in thinking to cultivate solidarity among the nations across the world: "an appropriate and authentic openness to the world presupposes the capacity to be open to one's neighbour within a family of nations" (FT 151). What is important is that we remain interconnected. He would say how our interconnectivity has made us "powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of nations" (FT 96). He articulates the interrelatedness of humanity theologically, saying: "Human beings are so made that they cannot live, develop and find fulfilment except 'in the sincere gift of self to others'" (FT 87).

Pope Francis explains the role of interrelatedness and interdependence for the unity and common destiny of the nations in the following way: "The ever-increasing number of interconnections and communications in today's world makes us powerfully aware of the unity and common destiny of the nations. In the dynamics of history, and the diversity of ethnic groups, societies and cultures, we see the seeds of a vocation to form a community composed of brothers and sisters who accept and care for one another" (FT 96).

4. Society that Opens to the Needs of the World

Pope Francis invites us to foster a heart open to the whole world that allows us to see that our well-being is tied up to that of our neighbours near and far, that “to attain fulfilment in life we need others” (FT 150). In chapter four, titled “A Heart Open to the Whole World” he discusses some of the practical political applications of universal fraternity, particularly one of the central political challenges of our time: immigration. According to him, everyone has the right to migrate to “meet their basic needs and those of their families” (FT 129). He has reiterated his call for a more welcoming attitude toward migrants, saying that everyone has the right to “dream of a better future.” He says: “If every human being possesses an inalienable dignity, if all people are my brothers and sisters, and if the world truly belongs to everyone, then it matters little whether my neighbour was born in my country or elsewhere” (FT 125). This is because “each country also belongs to the foreigner, inasmuch as a territory’s goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere” (FT 124).

Pope Francis supports the cause of immigrants, saying: “No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this” (FT 121). He is convinced that “each country also belongs to the foreigner inasmuch as a territory’s goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere” (FT 124). He quotes Moses’ exhortation to Israelites to call his concern for the migrants: ““you shall not wrong or oppress a stranger, for you were strangers in the land of Egypt’ (Ex 22:21)” (FT 61).

Pope Francis appeals to countries to welcome, protect, promote, and integrate migrants, especially for those fleeing serious humanitarian crises. These include: “developing and simplifying the granting of visas, opening humanitarian corridors, providing

housing, security and essential services, offering work and training opportunities, promoting family reunification, protecting minors, guaranteeing religious freedom” (FT 129). He says that “ideally, unnecessary migration ought to be avoided” (FT 129). Nobody should feel forced to leave their place of origin and be uprooted from their family, religion, and culture (cf FT 38). While we must make efforts to reduce migration, Pope Francis says that we are “obliged to respect the right of all individuals to find a place that meets their basic needs and those of their families” (FT 129). Rather than considering immigrants as a threat to the country, he says, they enrich a country, and their presence is “a gift” (FT133). He criticizes that most wealthy nations see immigrants as “usurpers who have nothing to offer” (FT 141). He also emphasizes the enrichment of the cultures by mutual encounters with one another, and he specifically mentions how the immigrants have enriched the United States, as well as how Jewish immigrants blessed his home country of Argentina (FT 135).

Pope Francis argues that “The world exists for everyone because all of us were born with the same dignity” and “the Christian tradition has never recognized the right to private property as absolute or inviolable” for “the right to private property can only be considered a secondary natural right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods” (FT 118, 120). He takes the principle “the world exists for everyone” further saying:

Nowadays, a firm belief in the common destination of the earth’s goods requires that this principle also be applied to nations, their territories and their resources. Seen from the standpoint not only of the legitimacy of private property and the rights of its citizens but also of the first principle of the common destination of

goods, we can then say that each country also belongs to the foreigner, inasmuch as a territory's goods must not be denied to a needy person coming from elsewhere. As the Bishops of the United States have taught, there are fundamental rights that 'precede any society because they flow from the dignity granted to each person as created by God' (FT 124).

Pope Francis urges us to resist "the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people" (FT 27). He warns that "those who raise walls will end up as slaves within the very walls they have built" (FT 27). In short, Pope Francis' vision of an "open-world" can be "summarized in four words: welcome, protect, promote and integrate. For it is not a case of implementing welfare programs from the top-down, but rather of undertaking a journey together, through these four actions" (FT 129). He cautions not to narrow our minds and hearts: "Let us realize that as our minds and hearts narrow, the less capable we become of understanding the world around us" (FT 147). He asks us "to think not simply as a country but also as part of the larger human family" (FT 141).

5. Society that Fosters Healthy Neighbourhood in the World

Pope Francis' call to be neighbours in the world is very hopes giving. He asks us "not to decide who is close enough to be our neighbour, but rather that we ourselves become neighbours to all" (FT 80). In the second chapter, titled "A Stranger on the Road," he presents the Samaritan who helped a traveller who had been left for dead as a model of human fraternity, in contrast to others who passed by (Lk 10: 25-37). According to him, this parable provides insights into the deep connections that bond all humans as brothers and sisters, and it functions as a "ray of light in the

midst of what we are experiencing” (FT 56). He considers this parable an invitation from Jesus to “rediscover our vocation as citizens of our respective nations and the entire world, builders of a new social bond” (FT 66). According to him, it “speaks to us of an essential and often forgotten aspect of our common humanity: we were created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love” (FT 68).

Pope Francis asks us to discern to be Good Samaritans in our day-to-day life: “Each day we have to decide whether to be Good Samaritans or indifferent bystanders” (FT 69). He says that our efforts for fraternity should become a “vocation,” a calling that shakes us from our sinful habits (FT 66). He says that each new day should be seen as an opportunity to “include, integrate, and lift up the fallen” rather than “an arena for [our] own power plays” (FT 77). He reiterates the teaching of the apostle of James: “Those who do not love a brother or sister whom they have seen, cannot love God whom they have not seen (1 Jn 4:20)” (FT 61). He is concerned about our indifference towards a suffering person, and he says that it is a symptom of an unhealthy society: “The sight of a person who is suffering disturbs us. It makes us uneasy since we have no time to waste on other people’s problems. These are symptoms of an unhealthy society” (FT 65). He considers it as a grave mistake not to care for the weakest and most fragile: “We need to acknowledge that we are constantly tempted to ignore others, especially the weak. Let us admit that, for all the progress we have made, we are still “illiterate” when it comes to accompanying, caring for and supporting the most frail and vulnerable members of our developed societies” (FT 64).

Pope Francis even praises those unbelievers who become true Samaritans and thus do the will of God for humanity: “Paradoxically, those who claim to be unbelievers can sometimes put God’s will into practice better than believers”

(FT 74). He urges them to follow the teaching of Jesus by not setting limits on who they regard as their neighbours. He says that love builds bridges, and we “are made for love” (FT 88), urging Christians, in particular, to recognize Christ in the face of all those who are excluded (FT 85).

He reminds us that the parable of the Good Samaritan makes us aware of our responsibility “for the fragility of others” and moves us to “set aside” our desires and goals “before the concrete gaze of those who are most vulnerable” (FT 115). He exhorts us to “go outside the self to find a fuller existence in another” (FT 88) “toward universal communion” (FT 95).

6. Society that Overcomes the Dark Clouds over a Closed World

In the first chapter, titled “Dark Clouds over a Closed World,” Pope Francis makes a frank assessment of a world in turmoil, and he tells that there are many serious issues currently preventing us from living as true brothers and sisters with common goals. He denounces the selfishness and the disinterest in the common good, the prevalence of a market logic based on profit and the culture of waste, unemployment, racism, poverty etc., which hinder universal brotherhood. He states that tendencies of isolationism, nationalism, a global economy that promotes individual interests, a loss of the sense of history, deconstructionism, limitless consumption wastefulness, the lack of concern for the environment, and a throwaway culture are blocking to achieving this goal of universal fraternity (cf. FT 13 & 18). He points out that globalization has created only an illusion of giving a sense of belonging to a common family, but it only drove toward a “globalized indifference” (FT 30).

In today’s world, the sense of belonging to a single human family is fading, and the dream of working together for justice and peace seems an outdated utopia,” ...“What reigns instead is a

cool, comfortable and globalized indifference, born of deep disillusionment concealed behind a deceptive illusion: thinking that we are all-powerful, while failing to realize that we are all in the same boat (FT30).

According to Pope Francis, the farfetched individual concerns play a vital role in the rejection of the dignity and well-being of the whole of humanity:

The gap between concern for one's personal well-being and the prosperity of the larger human family seems to be stretching to the point of complete division between individuals and human community ... It is one thing to feel forced to live together, but something entirely different to value the richness and beauty of those seeds of common life that need to be sought out and cultivated" (FT 31).

Pope Francis identifies one's fears and doubts as to the root cause for intolerance against the other, leading even to racism: "There is a problem when doubts and fears condition our way of thinking and acting to the point of making us intolerant, closed and perhaps even without realizing it racist" (FT 41). He criticizes "culture of walls" that favours the proliferation of mafias, fueled by fear and loneliness: "new walls are erected for self-preservation...we encounter "the temptation to build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land, to prevent this encounter with other cultures, with other people "(FT 27).

Intolerance and Social Exclusion

Pope Francis considers racism as an attitude that can be compared to "a virus that quickly mutates and, instead of

disappearing, goes into hiding, and lurks in waiting” (FT 97). Quoting the U.S. bishops’ 2018 pastoral letter against racism, “Open Wide Our Hearts,” he condemns this inhuman behaviour saying there are fundamental rights that “precede any society because they flow from the dignity granted to each person as created by God (FT 124). He also alludes to the “hidden exiles,” that is people with disabilities, “who are treated as foreign bodies in society (FT 76). Many persons with disabilities “feel that they exist without belonging and without participating” (FT 98). However, he feels that we can overcome the barriers of intolerance and seek the truth through dialogue and passionate conversation: “Together, we can seek the truth in dialogue, in relaxed conversation or in passionate debate. To do so calls for perseverance; it entails moments of silence and suffering, yet it can patiently embrace the broader experience of individuals and peoples” (FT 50).

In a world where gender discrimination and exploitation exist, Pope Francis strives to ensure the dignity of women globally so that the dream of the universal fraternity will have its desired fruits. For he says, “The organization of societies worldwide is still far from reflecting clearly that women possess the same dignity and identical rights as men” (FT 23).

A Culture of “Throwaway”

While there were promising movements of unity and fraternity among nations and peoples, Pope Francis says that we are showing “signs of a certain regression” in growing in collaboration and extending friendship to the nations (FT 11). He feels that the entire world is drawn into a form of globalism that neglects authentic fraternity and instead offers “cool, comfortable, and globalized indifference” (FT 30). He attributes this mainly to the throwaway culture favouring a crude utilitarian view of the economy and humanity itself (FT 22). According to him, the “throwaway world” promotes abortion and euthanasia, neglect of the elderly, discrimination against women, slavery, etc.

In this “throwaway world”, he feels that “persons are no longer seen as a paramount value to be cared for and respected, especially when they are poor and disabled, ‘not yet useful’ – like the unborn, or ‘no longer needed’ – like the elderly” (FT 18).

Pope Francis warns against the tendencies of the throwaway culture of the modern world, and he exhorts us to consider that “loving the most insignificant of human beings as a brother as if there were no one else in the world but him, cannot be considered a waste of time” (FT 193):

The modern world, with its technical advances, tends increasingly to functionalize the satisfaction of human desires, now classified and subdivided among different services. Less and less will people be called by name, less and less will this unique being be treated as a person with his or her feelings, sufferings, problems, joys and family. Their illnesses will be known only in order to cure them, their financial needs only to provide for them, their lack of a home only to give them lodging, their desires for recreation and entertainment only to satisfy them”. Yet it must never be forgotten that “loving the most insignificant of human beings as a brother, as if there were no one else in the world but him, cannot be considered a waste of time (FT 193).

Digital “Non-Connectivity”

Despite the increase in digital communication in response to our obvious need for engagement, Pope Francis says that “Digital connectivity is not enough to build bridges. It is not capable of uniting humanity” (FT 43). He articulates how digital communication can bring havoc in society, such as

remarkable hostility, insults, abuse, defamation, verbal violence, etc. (FT 44). He argues that “Persons or situations we find unpleasant or disagreeable are simply deleted in today’s virtual networks; a virtual circle is then created, isolating us from the real world in which we are living” (FT 47). However, Pope Francis says that media can foster solidarity and a more dignified life for all:

In today’s globalized world, “the media can help us to feel closer to one another, creating a sense of the unity of the human family which in turn can inspire solidarity and serious efforts to ensure a more dignified life for all... We need constantly to ensure that present-day forms of communication are in fact guiding us to generous encounter with others, to honest pursuit of the whole truth, to service, to closeness to the underprivileged and to the promotion of the common good (FT 205).

7. Society that Fosters a Culture of Fraternity

Pope Francis suggests that universal fraternity and social friendship must be rooted in an authentic cultural encounter that resists the temptation to “build a culture of walls, to raise walls, walls in the heart, walls on the land” (FT 27). He sees the possibility for a beautiful integration of one’s own culture while striving for the common good of the whole of humanity. “Each particular group becomes part of the fabric of universal communion and there discovers its own beauty. All individuals, whatever their origin, know that they are part of the greater human family, without which they will not be able to understand themselves fully” (FT 149).

However, Pope Francis also stresses the need to stay grounded in one’s own cultural identity and not be driven by “a false openness to the universal, born of the shallowness of those lacking insight

into the genius of their native land” (FT 145). He argues that receptivity and mutual acceptance will come only when we get rooted in our own culture: “I can welcome others who are different, and value the unique contribution they have to make, only if I am rooted in my own people and culture. [. . .] The common good likewise requires that we protect and love our native land” (FT 143). According to him, cultural enrichment is a “healthy and enriching exchange” (FT 144), and “a healthy openness never threatens one’s own identity” (FT 148). He also says that it applies to our approach to the other faiths. Rather than “watering down” (FT 151) one’s own beliefs, each side must hold its own beliefs firmly for authentic dialogue to be possible. Only then can one culture (or religion) “be nourished” by another (FT 148).

Pope Francis also articulates that rootedness in one’s own cultural identity is fundamental for social cohesion and dialogue with other cultures.

“Just as there can be no dialogue with ‘others’ without a sense of our own identity, so there can be no openness between peoples except on the basis of love for one’s own land, one’s own people, one’s own cultural roots. I cannot truly encounter another unless I stand on firm foundations, for it is on the basis of these that I can accept the gift the other brings and in turn offer an authentic gift of my own. I can welcome others who are different, and value the unique contribution they have to make, only if I am firmly rooted in my own people and culture” (FT 143).

Pope Francis does not propose “a completely enclosed, a-historic, static ‘indigenism’ that would reject any kind of blending (mestizaje)” (FT 148). This mutual enrichment,

which he calls “mestizaje,” a word derived from mestizo, describes a true, healthy openness:

A living culture, enriched by elements from other places, does not import a mere carbon copy of those new elements, but integrates them in its own unique way. The result is a new synthesis that is ultimately beneficial to all, since the original culture itself ends up being nourished. That is why I have urged indigenous peoples to cherish their roots and their ancestral cultures ... The world grows and is filled with new beauty, thanks to the successive syntheses produced between cultures that are open and free of any form of cultural imposition” (FT 148).

He says that disdain of one’s own culture is nothing more than a kind of elitism: “This is a far cry from the false universalism of those who constantly travel abroad because they cannot tolerate or love their people. Those who look down on their people tend to create within society categories of the first and second class, people of greater or lesser dignity, people enjoying greater or fewer rights” (FT 99). He questions the cultural integrity of those who look down on their own people: “There can be a false openness to the universal, born of the shallowness of those lacking insight into the genius of their native land or harbouring unresolved resentment towards their own people” (FT 145).

According to Pope Francis, what is at stake is a kind of cross-pollination between cultures, in which they enrich one another while preserving their own cultural richness: “The path to peace does not mean making society blandly uniform, but getting people to work together, side-by-side, in pursuing goals that benefit everyone” (FT 228).

8. Society that Fosters a Culture of Dialogue

According to Pope Francis, an authentic dialogue requires an abiding presence with others, even those we disagree with or dislike, sometimes “in relaxed conversation or passionate debate” (FT 50). According to him, dialogue is a middle path between “selfish indifference” and “violent protest” (FT 198). True dialogue is much more than a monologue, debate or back-and-forth arguing. Rather it is a process involving: “Approaching, speaking, listening, looking at, coming to know and understand one another, and to find common ground: all these things are summed up in the one word “dialogue”” (FT 198). He says that monologues engage no one (FT 200). Whenever people are unafraid to get to the heart of an issue, the interests of society, consensus and the reality of objective truth can be harmonized in authentic dialogue (FT 212).

Pope Francis says that genuine dialogue has “the ability to respect the other’s point of view and to admit that it may include legitimate convictions and concerns” (FT 203). He believes that genuine dialogue does not come at the sacrifice of justice and truth: “We need to learn how to unmask the various ways that the truth is manipulated, distorted and concealed in public and private discourse” (FT 208). According to him, genuine dialogue allows us to discover those shared values we know to be true and fosters a consensus among and within societies that becomes the basis for a shared social ethic:

In a pluralistic society, dialogue is the best way to realize what ought always to be affirmed and respected apart from any ephemeral consensus. Such dialogue needs to be enriched and illumined by clear thinking, rational arguments, a variety of perspectives and the contribution of different

fields of knowledge and points of view. ... Our understanding of their meaning and scope can increase – and in that respect, consensus is a dynamic reality – but in themselves, they are held to be enduring by virtue of their inherent meaning (FT 211).

Pope Francis suggests the path of dialogue, which seeks congruence between “the interests of society, consensus and the reality of objective truth. These three realities can be harmonized whenever, through dialogue, people are unafraid to get to the heart of an issue” (FT 212). Society is built on authentic dialogue, which involves respecting the other’s viewpoint: “it must respect the truth of our human dignity and submit to that truth” (FT 207). To explain the nature of the authentic dialogue, he draws on a favourite image, that of the polyhedron, “whose different sides form a variegated unity, in which ‘the whole is greater than the part’” (FT 215).

9. Society that Fosters a Culture of Encounter

Pope Francis calls for a new culture – a “culture of encounter” rooted in bridge building and community: “Life, for all its confrontations, is the art of encounter” (FT 215). He says that everyone is indispensable and can learn from each other: “Each of us can learn something from others. No one is useless and no one is expendable” (FT 215). He suggests for a culture of encounter “capable of transcending our differences and divisions. He places “culture of encounter” as a new culture and a style of life: “a “culture of encounter” means that we, as a people, should be passionate about meeting others, seeking points of contact, building bridges, planning a project that includes everyone. This becomes an aspiration and a style of life” (FT 216).

Pope Francis says that the “culture of encounter” should take place at all levels of society: “Encounter cannot take place only between the holders of economic, political or academic power.

Genuine social encounter calls for a dialogue that engages the culture shared by the majority of the population” (FT 219). True encounter does not push others away because they make us uncomfortable. It is rooted in a “basic sense of belonging” to each other which is present within each human being (FT 230). It does not mean avoiding conflicts or “making society blandly uniform” (FT 228). Political leaders practising encounter would foster reconciliation that happens through “open, honest, and patient negotiation” (FT 244). Moreover, he calls the international community to work for a culture of tolerance: “the architects of international policy and world economy to work strenuously to spread the culture of tolerance and of living together in peace; to intervene at the earliest opportunity to stop the shedding of innocent blood” (FT 192).

10. Society that Fosters Human Dignity

According to Pope Francis, an authentic human fraternity recognizes the inherent dignity of all persons. It takes care of the person’s integral development by giving “sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development” (FT 118). He believes that if we are willing to dream together of a world firmly grounded on the dignity of all persons, “we can rise to the challenge of envisaging a new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127).

Pope Francis says that our commitment to the dignity of every person and the common good must guide our relationships, civil institutions, and economic systems so that all people have the opportunity to “develop integrally” (FT 108). He is convinced that “the dignity of others is to be respected in all circumstances, not because that dignity is something we have invented or imagined, but because human beings possess an intrinsic worth” that comes from God (FT

213). According to him, peace would require “to place at the center of all political, social and economic activity the human person, who enjoys the highest dignity, and respect for the common good” (FT 232).

Pope Francis affirms that “God has created all human beings with equal rights, duties, and dignity, and has called them to live together as brothers and sisters” (FT 5). He further asserts that human dignity is the basis of the common good and universal brotherhood: “When the dignity of the human person is respected, and his or her rights recognized and guaranteed, creativity and interdependence thrive, and the creativity of the human personality is released through actions that further the common good” (FT 22). He places human dignity and respect for the common good are central to end to the building of a country’s social peace:

Individually and together, we must commit and work to eradicate the oppression and selfish greed that dehumanizes others for personal or national gain. “There is no end to the building of a country’s social peace. Rather, it requires us to place at the centre of all political, social and economic activity the human person, who enjoys the highest dignity, and respect for the common good” (FT 232).

In the context of human dignity and uniqueness of human life, Pope Francis’s teaching on capital punishment becomes very significant. He states clearly that “the death penalty is inadmissible and the Catholic Church is firmly committed to calling for its abolition worldwide” (FT 263). He condemns the death penalty because it rejects the dignity of human persons. He explains it in the following way: “The firm rejection of the death penalty shows to what extent it is possible to recognize the inalienable dignity of every human being and to accept that he or she has a place in this universe” (FT 269). He exhorts to heal the

wounds of the souls rather than taking punitive measures. He says, “Do not let the atrocity of their sins feed a desire for vengeance, but desire instead to heal the wounds which those deeds have inflicted on their souls” (FT 256). He considers the death penalty as a symptom of a society that has lost awareness of its interconnectedness and disregards the dignity of the human person (FT 263). He extends this call further to improve the quality of prison conditions, which is another example of how we deny our brothers and sisters authentic encounter and social friendship (FT 268).

11. Society that Fosters Opportunity and Dignity of Human Labour

According to Pope Francis, the best politics is also one that protects the dignity of employment, an “essential dimension of social life ... personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts” (FT 162). He considers employment as the biggest issue for a developed society: “The biggest issue is employment. The truly “popular” thing – since it promotes the good of the people – is to provide everyone with the opportunity to nurture the seeds that God has planted in each of us: our talents, our initiative and our innate resources” (FT 162). He further says that “In a genuinely developed society, work is an essential dimension of social life, for it is not only a means of earning one’s daily bread, but also of personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts. Work gives us a sense of shared responsibility for the development of the world, and ultimately, for our life as a people” (FT 162). According to him, the best help that we can give to the poor is to provide them with employment, because it is a path to “a life of dignity”: “This is the finest help we can give to the poor, the best path to a life of dignity. Hence my insistence that

“helping the poor financially must always be a provisional solution in the face of pressing needs. The broader objective should always be to allow them a dignified life through work” (FT 162). He categorically says that “there is no poverty worse than that which takes away work and the dignity of work” (FT 162).

Pope Francis believes that jobs that pay a living wage and honour the dignity of the human person are essential. He writes, “In a genuinely developed society, work is an essential dimension of social life, for it is not only a means of earning one’s daily bread, but also of personal growth, the building of healthy relationships, self-expression and the exchange of gifts. Work gives us a sense of shared responsibility for the development of the world, and ultimately, for our life as a people” (FT 162). He says, “helping the poor financially must always be a provisional solution in the face of pressing needs. The broader objective should always be to allow them a dignified life through work” (FT 162).

12. Society that Fosters a Global Ethics of Solidarity and Cooperation

Pope Francis calls for global ethics of solidarity and cooperation for envisaging new humanity. By recalling his address on Nuclear Weapons, Nagasaki, Japan (November 24 2019), he says: “For a real and lasting peace will only be possible “on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127). He argues that “if we accept the great principle that there are rights born of our inalienable human dignity, we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity (FT 127). According to him, every person, because of their inalienable dignity, has a right to the goods necessary for “a developed and dignified life”, and “the limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this” (FT 121).

Pope Francis criticizes selfishness and wrong policies in the economy and handling common issues. So, in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, he writes that it has shown that “not everything can be resolved by market freedom” and that human dignity must be put “back at the center” (FT 168). Therefore, he denounces “the “dogma” of neoliberalism that the market by itself can resolve any problem, a dogma which repeatedly “resort[s] to the magic theories of ‘spillover’ or ‘trickle’” to solve any societal problem” (FT 168). The proper anti-poverty strategy, he thinks that it should be from the perspective of solidarity and subsidiarity (FT 187). According to him, it is not enough to “contain” poverty. Still, it should enable the poor to shape their future, and to participate in society: “What is needed are new pathways of self-expression and participation in society. Education serves these by making it possible for each human being to shape his or her own future. Here too, we see the importance of the principle of subsidiarity, which is inseparable from the principle of solidarity” (FT 187).

Pope Francis’ invitation to embody the love of the Good Samaritan is not merely a call to a new social ethic. It is also an invitation to remember the purpose of our life: “created for a fulfilment that can only be found in love. We cannot be indifferent to suffering. . . . Instead, we should feel indignant, challenged to emerge from our comfortable isolation, and to be changed by our contact with human suffering” (FT 68). According to him, the parable the Good Samaritan challenges us to prioritize the needs of the other and begin to “restore the dignity to the suffering and to build a society” that honours the human person and the common good of all (FT 71). He argues that “no one solution, no single acceptable methodology, no economic recipe can be applied indiscriminately to all” (FT 167). Therefore, what is needed

is global solidarity and cooperation for more fraternal humanity.

Pope Francis condemns an attitude of contempt or indifference for the poor, as well as the mentality of those who feel threatened by social programs for those in need, thinking these could “edge them out” from their current social status (FT 73). He exhorts the wealthy of the world that they must “care for and cultivate something that [they] possess, in such a way that it can contribute to the good of all” (FT 143). According to him, “Neoliberalism simply reproduces itself by resorting to the magic theories of “spillover” or “trickle” – without using the name – as the only solution to societal problems” (cf. FT 168). He believes that the market cannot resolve every problem, and the theory of “spillover” does not resolve the inequalities (FT 168). He argues that poverty cannot be measured according to “criteria from the past” but “must always be understood and gauged in the context of the actual opportunities available in each concrete historical period” (FT 21).

By quoting St. John Paul II’s encyclical *Centesimus Annus* no.35, Pope Francis also addresses the question of foreign debt and the fate of the developing countries: “the fundamental right of peoples to subsistence and progress” [...] is at times severely restricted by the pressure created by foreign debt. [...] While respecting the principle that all legitimately acquired debt must be repaid, how many poor countries fulfil this obligation should not end up compromising their very existence and growth” (FT 126). By quoting his predecessor Benedict XVI, *Caritas in Veritate* no. 67, he argues that poorer countries need to be given a fair shake and “an effective voice in shared decision-making” (FT 138).

Pope Francis reminded us of the interdependence and shared responsibility of the whole human family. Therefore, he says that each country must feel responsible for people who are not born in it. Unfortunately, this Christian worldview today, according to him, is rejected by individualistic liberal approaches (cf. FT 163),

and he exhorts the Christians to reject nationalism which views society as merely the sum of coexisting interests (FT 163) and to welcome immigrants with love (FT 129-132).

Pope Francis argues that the right to live in dignity cannot be denied to anyone because rights are without borders, and no one can remain excluded according to his or her place of birth:

“No one, then, can remain excluded because of his or her place of birth, much less because of privileges enjoyed by others who were born in lands of greater opportunity. The limits and borders of individual states cannot stand in the way of this. As it is unacceptable that some have fewer rights by virtue of being women, it is likewise unacceptable that the mere place of one’s birth or residence should result in his or her possessing fewer opportunities for a developed and dignified life” (FT 121).

For the same reason, Pope Francis affirms that the “rights to free enterprise or market freedom” cannot “supersede the rights of peoples” and “respect for the natural environment”: “The right of some to free enterprise or market freedom cannot supersede the rights of peoples and the dignity of the poor, or, for that matter, respect for the natural environment, for “if we make something our own, it is only to administer it for the good of all” (FT 122; cf. LS 95).

13. Society that Fosters Inclusive Economy

The Catechism of the Catholic Church defines “common good” as “the sum total of social conditions which allow people, either as groups or as individuals, to reach their fulfilment more fully and more easily” (CCC 1906). It is in

tune with this teaching that Pope Francis spells out his vision of universal destination of created goods for a more fraternal society. His basic presumption for universal destination of created goods is that “the world exists for everyone” (FT 118), and he is very clear that the “privileges of some” over “the right of all” cannot be justified from “differences of colour, religion, talent, place of birth or residence”:

The world exists for everyone because all of us were born with the same dignity. Differences of colour, religion, talent, place of birth or residence, and so many others, cannot be used to justify the privileges of some over the rights of all. As a community, we have an obligation to ensure that every person lives with dignity and has sufficient opportunities for his or her integral development (FT 118).

Pope Francis restates the Church’s teaching of the “common destination of created goods,” which states that “if one person lacks what is necessary to live with dignity, it is because another person is detaining it” (FT 119). He believes that “if we accept the great principle that there are rights born of inalienable human dignity, we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127). According to him, “Unless the rights of each individual are harmoniously ordered to the greater good, those rights will end up being considered limitless and consequently will become a source of conflicts and violence” (FT 111).

Pope Francis bases the Fathers of the Church to substantiate his arguments for the universal destination of created goods, and he quotes Saints John Chrysostom, Gregory the Great, Basil, Peter Chrysologus, Augustine etc.:

In the first Christian centuries, a number of thinkers developed a universal vision in their

reflections on the common destination of created goods. This led them to realize that if one person lacks what is necessary to live with dignity, it is because another person is detaining it. Saint John Chrysostom summarizes it in this way: “Not to share our wealth with the poor is to rob them and take away their livelihood. The riches we possess are not our own, but theirs as well”. In the words of Saint Gregory the Great, “When we provide the needy with their basic needs, we are giving them what belongs to them, not to us (FT 119).

Pope Francis also quotes St. John Paul II to validate his arguments on universal destination of created goods: “God gave the earth to the whole human race for the sustenance of all its members, without excluding or favouring anyone” (FT 120; cf. *Centessimus Annus* 31). He quotes St. John Paul II from his encyclical *Laborem Exercens* again: “The principle of the common use of created goods is the “first principle of the whole ethical and social order” [FT 120; cf. *Laborem exercens*, 19] and he also cites from the Compendium of the Social Doctrine of the Church by the Pontifical Council for Justice and Peace, “it is a natural and inherent right that takes priority over others” (FT 120). His proposal for the universal destination of goods “calls for an alternative way of thinking” (FT 127). He believes that if we are willing to dream together of a world firmly grounded on the dignity of all persons, “we can rise to the challenge of envisaging new humanity. We can aspire to a world that provides land, housing and work for all” (FT 127).

14. Society that Fosters Inclusive Property Rights

Pope Francis mentions that most of us live in unjust economies, even if we are not suffering ourselves. At the root of the disparity between the poor and rich, he says it is a “profit-based economic model” (FT 22). He reiterates John Paul II’s teaching in *Centesimus Annus*,

In fact, the purpose of a business firm is not simply to make a profit but is to be found in its very existence as a community of persons who in various ways are endeavouring to satisfy their basic needs, and who form a particular group at the service of the whole of society. Profit is a regulator of the life of a business, but it is not the only one; other human and moral factors must also be considered which, in the long term, are at least equally important for the life of a business (FT 35).

Pope Francis believes that market freedom and efficiency do not give place for disabled, the poor and the uneducated people because “If a society is governed primarily by the criteria of market freedom and efficiency, there is no place for such persons, and fraternity will remain just another vague ideal” (FT 109). He urges that the “right to private property” be accompanied by the “prior principle” of “subordination of all private property to the universal destination of the earth’s goods, and thus the right of all to their use” (FT 123). Therefore, he never disowns capitalism but asks for proper use of the wealth. He considers the right to property as a responsibility for the care for all: “All this brings out the positive meaning of the property right: I care for and cultivate something that I possess, in such a way that it can contribute to the good of all” (FT 143). Thus, private property can only be considered a secondary natural right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods: “The right to private property can only be considered a secondary natural

right, derived from the principle of the universal destination of created goods (FT 120). But he complains that very often that this secondary right overrides the primary rights: “This has concrete consequences that ought to be reflected in the workings of society. Yet it often happens that secondary rights displace primary and overriding rights, in practice making them irrelevant” (FT 120).

Pope Francis also reiterates his teaching on “right to private property” from his earlier Encyclical *Laudato Si*: “the Christian tradition has never recognized the right to private property as absolute or inviolable, and has stressed the social purpose of all forms of private property” (FT 120; LS 93). He further refers to his earlier teachings to bring this point for: “The right to private property is always accompanied by the primary and prior principle of the subordination of all private property to the universal destination of the earth’s goods, and thus the right of all to their use”(FT 12; cf. LS 93; EG 189-190).

Indeed, Pope Francis considers “business activity is essentially ‘a noble vocation, directed to producing wealth and improving our world’” (FT 123). Moreover, he argues, a certain self-interest, including the taking of profit, is not repugnant to the moral purpose of economic activity: “In God’s plan, each individual is called to promote his or her own development, and this includes finding the best economic and technological means of multiplying goods and increasing wealth” (FT 123). He reminds us of our shared responsibility to care for the other and to have a more fraternal sharing with those in need.

15. Society that fosters a Politics at the Service of the Common Good

Pope Francis calls for a “better kind of politics” to find solutions for global problems. According to him, a “better kind of politics” is one that places itself at the service of the common good (FT 180). In the context of migration and refugee issues, he writes, “states are not able, on their own, to implement adequate solutions, ‘since the consequences of the decisions made by each inevitably has repercussions on the entire international community’” (FT 132). He reiterates that “politics must not be subject to the economy,” an appeal that he has made in his previous encyclical, *Laudato Si* (LS 189): “Here I would once more observe that “politics must not be subject to the economy, nor should the economy be subject to the dictates of an efficiency-driven paradigm of technocracy” (FT 177). He calls for a model of social, political and economic participation “that can include popular movements and invigorate local, national and international governing structures with that torrent of moral energy that springs from including the excluded in the building of a common destiny” (FT 169).

Pope Francis considers a “better kind of politics” as “a politics which is far-sighted and capable of a new, integral and interdisciplinary approach to handling the different aspects of the crisis.”... a “healthy politics... capable of reforming and coordinating” (FT 177). He is convinced that “we cannot expect economics to do this, nor can we allow economics to take over the real power of the state” (FT 177); a politics that “guarantees a sustainable equality” which executes “welfare projects, which meet certain urgent needs” (FT 161). According to him, “Good politics will seek ways of building communities at every level of social life, to recalibrate and reorient globalization and thus avoid its disruptive effects” (FT 182). In this context, he calls for global governance for migration that can open up long-term projects (129-132).

16. Society that Fosters “Political love” for Universal Fraternity

Pope Francis’ call to universal fraternity demands a political and social order built on charity and a shared pursuit of the common good. By using the term “political love,” Pope Francis shows us that there is another way to approach public life and that we can use politics to serve the common good without excluding anyone. According to him, political love is not unrealistic, for he says, “Recognizing that all people are our brothers and sisters, and seeking forms of social friendship that include everyone, is not merely utopian. It demands a decisive commitment to devising effective means to this end. Any effort along these lines becomes a noble exercise of charity” (FT 180). The “political love” that Pope Francis is asking is, in fact, a practical love, that is a “social love” (FT 183), a term that he borrows from John Paul II’s Encyclical *Redemptor Hominis* (RH 15). Political charity is also a spirit of openness to everyone as he articulates: “Government leaders can help to create” a beautiful polyhedral reality in which everyone has a place” (FT 190).

In contrast to populism that exploits the vulnerable and liberalism that serves the interests of the powerful (FT 155), Pope Francis says that political charity seeks the common good and help for those left behind (FT 165). According to him, we must seek “an integral human development that goes beyond ‘the idea of social policies being a policy for the poor, but never with the poor and never of the poor, much less part of a project that reunites peoples’” (FT 169). He proposes this as the norm for the international community, “where subsidiarity and solidarity work together in a complementary way” (FT 175), and therefore, he says that we must look for a political love that seeks “new ways of approaching the problems of today’s world, of profoundly renewing

structures, social organizations and legal systems from within” (FT 183).

Pope Francis explains that “political charity” is vital for a just and fair society:

There is a kind of love that is “elicited”: its acts proceed directly from the virtue of charity and are directed to individuals and peoples. There is also a “commanded” love, expressed in those acts of charity that spur people to create more sound institutions, more just regulations, more supportive structures (...). It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, even if we do not know that person, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering (FT 186).

According to Pope Francis, social charity is more than just good intentions (FT 185), but a commitment to solidarity with our sisters and brothers: “It is an act of charity to assist someone suffering, but it is also an act of charity, even if we do not know that person, to work to change the social conditions that caused his or her suffering” (FT 186). Political love is practised in sacrifice for those in greatest need, and therefore, it does not become “a soulless pragmatism” (FT 187), and it looks for “fruitfulness” against “results”: “what is important is not constantly achieving great results... It is truly noble to place our hope in the hidden power of the seeds of goodness we sow, and thus to initiate processes whose fruits will be reaped by others” (194-195).

In chapter three, titled “Envisaging and Engendering an Open World”, Pope Francis presents love as “universal dimension” (FT 83) for “envisaging and engendering an open world” (FT 87). He explains it quoting St. Thomas Aquinas that “love made possible by God’s grace as a movement outwards towards another,

whereby we consider ‘the beloved as somehow united to ourselves’” (FT 93). He affirms the power of love towards universal communion, saying that true love “impels us towards universal communion... By its very nature, love calls for growth in openness and the ability to accept others as part of a continuing adventure that makes every periphery converge in a greater sense of mutual belonging” (FT 95). He says that “the spiritual stature of a person’s life is measured by love,” (FT 92) but “some believers think that it consists in the imposition of their own ideologies upon everyone else, or a violent defence of the truth, or impressive demonstrations of strength” (FT 92). He never forgets to remind us of our responsibility of love: “All of us, as believers, need to recognize that love takes first place: love must never be put at risk, and the greatest danger lies in failing to love” (FT 92). Therefore, what is needed is a “universal love” that promotes the dignity of every human being (FT 106), and the value of solidarity (FT 114). Pope Francis says that it is love, Gospel love, “that impels us towards universal communion” (FT 95).

17. Society that Fosters a Global Network for a Fraternal Society

Pope Francis calls for a “new network of international relations” to ensure “the fundamental rights of people to subsistence and progress” (FT 126), a theme that he already dealt with in LS 51:

We are really speaking about a new network of international relations, since there is no way to resolve the serious problems of our world if we continue to think only in terms of mutual assistance between individuals or small groups. Nor should we forget that “inequity affects not only individuals but entire countries; it compels

us to consider an ethics of international relations (FT 126; cf. LS 51).

Taking the COVID-19 pandemic situation and our failure to handle it, Pope Francis says that we need are new models that focus on promoting human dignity and solidarity: He says: “the fragility of world-systems in the face of the pandemic has demonstrated that not everything can be resolved by market freedom” (FT 168). He is convinced that the common destination of the earth’s goods calls for a new way of understanding relations between countries:

This presupposes a different way of understanding relations and exchanges between countries. If every human being possesses an inalienable dignity, if all people are my brothers and sisters, and if the world truly belongs to everyone, then it matters little whether my neighbour was born in my country or elsewhere. My own country also shares responsibility for his or her development (FT 125).

Pope Francis also calls for more robust and more efficient organized international networking. According to him, the transnational nature of economic and financial sectors brings weakness of the power of nation-states: “The twenty-first century “is witnessing a weakening of the power of nation-states, chiefly because the economic and financial sectors, being transnational, tend to prevail over the political” (FT 172). It is therefore essential to devise stronger and more efficiently organized international institutions: “Given this situation, it is essential to devise stronger and more efficiently organized international institutions, with functionaries who are appointed fairly by agreement among national governments, and empowered to impose sanctions” (FT 172). Therefore, he urges to reform both of the international financial system and multilateral institutions such as the United Nations, saying it was vital for countries “to

establish shared goals and to ensure the worldwide observance of certain essential norms” (FT 174). By quoting Benedict XVI’s Encyclical Letter *Caritas in Veritate*, 67 Pope Francis says, “In this regard, I would also note the need for a reform of “the United Nations Organization, and likewise of economic institutions and international finance, so that the concept of the family of nations can acquire real teeth” (FT 173). According to the Pope, the UN must promote the force of law over the law of force by ensuring “tireless recourse to negotiation, mediation and arbitration” (FT 173).

18. Society that fosters Peace through Penitential Memory

Pope Francis asks us to cultivate a penitential memory to accept the past, not to cloud the future (FT 226). He encourages us to foster the opportunity for true reconciliation and forgiveness that honours the memories of past suffering and injustice by quoting the Message for the 2020 World Day of Peace: “We need to ‘keep alive the flame of collective conscience, bearing witness to succeeding generations to the horror of what happened,’ because that witness ‘awakens and preserves the memory of the victims, so that the conscience of humanity may rise up in the face of every desire for dominance and destruction” (FT 249). Forgiveness by those who have been harmed is the prophetic act of “break[ing] the vicious cycle; ... [and] halt[ing] the advance of the forces of destruction” (FT 251).

Pope Francis asserts that forgiveness and reconciliation are not passive. According to him, “reconciliation is a personal act”, and human evils like the Shoah and the atomic bombings must be remembered as symbols of the depths of human evil (246-247). He firmly believes that the value and

meaning of forgiveness should not be at the expense of renouncing our own rights: “loving an oppressor does not mean allowing him to keep oppressing us, or letting him think that what he does is acceptable. On the contrary, true love for an oppressor means seeking ways to make him cease his oppression” (FT 241). He affirms that “authentic reconciliation does not flee from conflict, but is achieved in conflict, resolving it through dialogue and open, honest and patient negotiation” (FT 244). He also emphasizes the inherent relationship between truth, justice and mercy: “Truth, in fact, is an inseparable companion of justice and mercy” (FT 227).

By quoting *Caritas in Veritate* 71-72, Pope Francis says that peace is not a product that can be manufactured through skill and technological know-how (FT 231). He says that peace requires an enduring commitment: “It is a patient effort to seek truth and justice, to honour the memory of victims and to open the way, step by step, to a shared hope stronger than the desire for vengeance” (FT 226). He compares the peace process with a “craft” in which everyone must do his or her part and whose task is never finished “a never-ending task” (FT 232). He further says that peace making process is a tireless commitment to restoring the dignity of every human person, especially of those who are often overlooked or ignored:

For peace “is not merely absence of war but a tireless commitment – especially on the part of those of us charged with greater responsibility – to recognize, protect and concretely restore the dignity, so often overlooked or ignored, of our brothers and sisters, so that they can see themselves as the principal protagonists of the destiny of their nation (FT 233)

According to Pope Francis, peace is, fundamentally, a process: “There is no end to the building of a country’s social peace; rather, it is an open-ended endeavour, a never-ending task that demands the commitment of everyone and challenges us to work

tirelessly to build the unity of the nation” (FT 232). Peacemaking is also a never-ending process and an “a real and lasting peace will only be possible on the basis of a global ethic of solidarity and cooperation in the service of a future shaped by interdependence and shared responsibility in the whole human family” (FT 127).

The so-called peace, according to Pope Francis, is merely an “apparent peace” created by politicians who silence the cry of the poor with promises of money but who do nothing to end the evil of inequality (EG 218, FT 236). He reminds us that “Those who work for tranquil social coexistence should never forget that inequality and lack of integral human development make peace impossible (FT 235).

19. Society that Rejects War and Conflicts

Pope Francis not only condemns war but also considers it as a “failure of politics” (FT 261). According to him, war is a “constant threat” that represents “the negation of all rights” (FT 257), the “failure of politics and humanity,” “a shameful capitulation” before the forces of evil” (FT 261). He is convinced that total elimination of nuclear weapons is a moral and humanitarian imperative: “the ultimate goal of the total elimination of nuclear weapons becomes both a challenge and a moral and humanitarian imperative” (FT 262). He is convinced that the most dreadful casualty of war is “the human family’s innate vocation to fraternity” (FT 26).

Pope Francis proposes a counterculture against war and military expenditures by offering a global effort to eradicate hunger in the world and favour development in the most impoverished countries: “With the money spent on weapons and other military expenditures, let us establish a global fund that can finally put an end to hunger and favour development in the most impoverished countries so that their citizens will

not resort to violent or illusory solutions, or have to leave their countries to seek a more dignified life” (FT 262).

While reflecting upon the moral legitimacy of just war, Pope Francis says, “it is easy to fall into an overly broad interpretation of this potential right. In this way, some would also wrongly justify even “preventive” attacks or acts of war that can hardly avoid entailing “evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated” (FT 258). He is convinced that wars can no longer be considered justifiable, as we cannot draw rational criteria: “it is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a just war” (FT 258). In a puzzling footnote (fn. 242), he disagrees with St. Augustine regarding just war, the Church Father who developed the concept of just war, and he says that St. Augustine “forged a concept of ‘just war’ that we no longer uphold in our own day,” and thus he rejects the “rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries” (FT 258). To substantiate his point, he quotes Pope St. John XXIII, who wrote in his encyclical *Pacem in Terris*, “It no longer makes sense to maintain that war is a fit instrument with which to repair the violation of justice.” He also strictly warns about how the traditional understanding of just war has been abused to justify every kind of war:

The Catechism of the Catholic Church speaks of the possibility of legitimate defence by means of military force, which involves demonstrating that certain ‘rigorous conditions of moral legitimacy’ have been met. Yet, it is easy to fall into an overly broad interpretation of this potential right ... In view of this, it is very difficult nowadays to invoke the rational criteria elaborated in earlier centuries to speak of the possibility of a ‘just war’. Never again war! (FT 258).

Pope Francis also criticizes war in the name of ‘preventive’ attacks saying, “some would also wrongly justify even

‘preventive’ attacks or acts of war that can hardly avoid entailing ‘evils and disorders graver than the evil to be eliminated’ (FT 258). He notes that “war can easily be chosen by invoking all sorts of allegedly humanitarian, defensive or precautionary excuses, and even resorting to the manipulation of information. In recent decades, every single war has been ostensibly ‘justified’” (FT 258) by its apologists.

Pope Francis categorically states that “violence has no basis in our fundamental religious convictions, but only in their distortion” (FT 282). He is convinced that we should not attempt to justify it “by invoking all sorts of allegedly humanitarian, defensive or precautionary excuses” (FT 258). Instead, we must understand the harsh reality that “every war leaves our world worse than it was before. War is a failure of politics and of humanity” (FT 261). Instead of getting entangled in “theoretical discussions,” he urges us to “touch the wounded flesh of the victims” (FT 261). According to him, war is an example of a broken solution to the conflict that has resulted in the “destruction in the fabric of national and global society” (FT 255). Instead of war, he asks us to foster kindness that “opens new paths where hostility and conflict would burn all bridges” (FT 224)

20. Society that Fosters Religious Harmony

Pope Francis highlights the role of religious communities in building a more fraternal world as outlined in the “Document on Human Fraternity” (FT 271). He says that our shared commitment to “witness to God” through word and action helps us to live with a “sincere heart” and “recognize one another as travelling companions, truly brothers and sisters” (FT 274). He is convinced that we have to focus on the message of peace that religions have in common, thereby recognizing that “universal communion with the entire

human family, [is] a vocation of all” (FT 277). He believes that all religions, “based on their respect for each human person as a creature called to be a child of God, contribute significantly to building human fraternity and defending justice in society” (FT 271). While religion can become a tool for violence and terrorism in the hands of unconscionable people, he invites people of all religions to return to that which are fundamental to all faith traditions: “worship of God and love for our neighbour” (FT 282).

Pope Francis calls for religious freedom in the journey towards fraternity and peace: “One fundamental human right must not be forgotten in the journey towards fraternity and peace. It is religious freedom for believers of all religions” (FT 279). Mutual respect and religious freedom challenge us to return to our sources and to work for a sustainable peace: “We believers are challenged to return to our sources, to concentrate on what is essential: worship of God and love for our neighbour, lest some of our teachings, taken out of context, end up feeding forms of contempt, hatred, xenophobia or negation of others. The truth is that violence has no basis in our fundamental religious convictions, but only in their distortion” (FT 282). He believes that the foundation of modern totalitarianism is the “denial of the transcendent dignity of the human person” and that violence “has no basis in religious convictions, but rather in their deformities” (FT 273). Pope Francis recalls that terrorism is not due to religion but to misinterpretations of religious texts and policies of hunger, poverty, injustice, and oppression (282-283).

According to Pope Francis, as believers in God, we are called to be true “people of dialogue,” to cooperate in building peace, not as intermediaries but as authentic mediators (FT 284). He believes that the Church cannot limit its influence to the private sphere and is responsible for participating in the public square to work for the common good (FT 276). According to him, being “catholic” means we are “called to take root in every place” and bring the wisdom of our tradition to the continual work for justice and integral human development (FT 278).

He cites the Document on Human Fraternity for World Peace and Common Coexistence, signed by him on February 4, 2019, in Abu Dhabi, with the Grand Imam of Al-Azhar, Ahmed Al-Tayyeb, to emphasize the fraternal call of different religious traditions: “In the name of God and of everything stated thus far, [we] declare the adoption of a culture of dialogue as the path; mutual cooperation as the code of conduct; reciprocal understanding as the method and standard” (FT 285).

Conclusion

As we have seen, *Fratelli Tutti* is Pope Francis’ reflection on human fraternity and universal brotherhood. He proposes universal fraternity and social friendship as antidotes for most of the social problems of contemporary society. *Fratelli Tutti* can be considered Pope Francis’ manifesto of the “social covenant” of human fraternity and social friendship for modern times. Here, he envisions a society that is open to all, includes all and values all. He dreams and invites us to dream together for a society that integrates everyone and fosters interrelatedness and interdependence. He visualizes a society that opens to the world’s needs and promotes a healthy neighbourhood in the world. He envisages a society that overcomes the evils of intolerance, social exclusion, racism, the culture of “throwaway”, and social media. He calls for a society that nurtures a culture of fraternity, dialogue, encounter, and tolerance. He foresees a society that raises human dignity and fosters the opportunity and dignity of human labour. He visualises a society that develops global ethics of solidarity and cooperation to find solutions for common issues. He dreams of a society that ensures an inclusive economy and assures property rights and the destination of the created goods for everyone in society. He calls for a better kind of politics at the service of the common

good, a politics that fosters “political love” and global network for a fraternal society. He envisages a society that realizes peace and reconciliation through penitential memory and forgiveness. He dreams a society that rejects war and conflicts; instead of a society that treasures integral growth and development of the nations and communities. Finally, he envisages a society that fosters religious harmony for building a more fraternal world. In short, *Fratelli Tutti* can be seen as a spiritual testament and social manifesto of Pope Francis for a better fraternal and universal brotherhood.

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A QUICK KEY TO *Fratelli Tutti*

Shadows over the closed world (Ch. 1) are spreading everywhere, leaving injured people by the roadside, cast out and discarded. The shadows plunge humanity into confusion, loneliness, and desolation. When we come upon an injured stranger on the road (Ch. 2), we can assume one of two attitudes: we can pass by or we can stop to help. The type of person we are and the type of political, social or religious group we belong to will be defined by whether we include or exclude the injured stranger.

God is universal love, and as long as we are part of that love and share in it, we are called to universal fraternity, which is openness to all. There are no "others," no "them," there is only "us". We want, with God and in God, an **open world** (Ch. 3), a world without walls, without borders, without people rejected, without strangers. To achieve this world, we must have an **open heart** (Ch. 4). We need to experience social friendship, seek what is morally good, and practice a social ethic because we know we are part of a universal fraternity. We are called to solidarity, encounter, and gratuitousness.

To create an open world with an open heart, it is necessary to engage in politics, and a **better kind of politics** (Ch. 5) is essential. Politics for the common

and universal good. Politics that is “popular” because it is for and with the people. It is politics with social charity that seeks human dignity. The politics of men and women who practice political love by integrating the economy with the social and cultural fabric into a consistent and life-giving human project.

Knowing how to **dialogue** is the way to open the world and build social friendship (Ch. 6) which manifests an open heart and provides the basis for a better politics. Dialogue seeks and respects the truth. Dialogue gives rise to the culture of encounter, which becomes a way of life, a passionate desire. Whoever dialogues is generous, recognizing and respecting the other.

But it is not enough just to engage in encounter. We have to face the reality of the injuries of past mis-encounters, and so we have to establish and walk the **paths of re-encounter** (Ch. 7). We need to heal the wounds, which requires seeking and offering forgiveness. To forgive is not to forget. We need to be daring and start from the truth—the recognition of historical truth—which is the inseparable companion of justice and mercy. All this is indispensable for advancing towards peace. Conflict is inevitable on the road to peace, but violence is inadmissible. That is why war is a recourse that must be rejected, and the death penalty a practice that must be eliminated.

The different religions of the world recognize human beings as God's creatures. As creatures, we are in a relationship of fraternity. **The religions** are called to the **service of fraternity in the world** (Ch. 8). In dialogue and with hearts open to the world, we can establish

social friendship and fraternity. In our openness to the Father of all, we recognize our universal condition as brothers and sisters. For Christians, the wellspring of human dignity and fraternity is in the Gospel of Jesus Christ, and that is what inspires our actions and commitments. This path of fraternity also has a Mother called Mary.

Faced with those injured by the shadows of a closed world and still lying by the roadside, we are invited by Pope Francis to make our own the world's desire for fraternity, starting with the recognition that we are “*Fratelli tutti*”, **brothers and sisters all**.

<https://www.usccb.org/resources/02-%20Quick%20Key%20to%20FRATELLI%20TUTTI%20-%20EN.pdf>
